

OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PILGRIMAGE TOURISM IN OUR REPUBLIC

Abstract:

This article describes the organizational and legal basis of the increase in the number of tourists visiting places of pilgrimage. Special attention is paid to the priority directions of tourism development in Uzbekistan, support measures, including the adoption of legal and regulatory documents.

Key words:

Tourism, historical cities, pilgrimage tourism, Bukhara, Samarkand, Shahrissabz

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We live in a rapidly developing world today. Like all industries, the tourism industry is developing rapidly. The reason is that people have the need to have cultural recreation, rest, walk and, most importantly, to visit. The concept of "pilgrimage" in ancient times was to seek refuge from God by visiting the great figures of our ancestors. In the countries of Central Asia, this is called a "pilgrimage", that is, a visit to holy places. In particular, on the implementation of the Action Strategy of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on 5 priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 on February 3, 2021, in the year of supporting the youth and strengthening the health of the population. According to the Decree No. PF-6155 on the program, a part of the expenses for traveling around Uzbekistan was reimbursed.

From time immemorial, Uzbekistan has been a crossroads of high civilization and culture. Representatives of different peoples and nationalities live a free and prosperous life in our republic, believing in their religions. Therefore, there is a great opportunity to attract visitors to pilgrimage tourism and increase the scope of Turkestan. In particular, in Samarkand, leading scientists from China, Russia, France, Italy, South Korea, Poland and Kazakhstan participated in the tourism sector. An example of this is the international scientific conference on the renaissance of pilgrimage tourism at the intersection of the Great Silk Road.

The Islamic culture of Uzbekistan and There are many sacred and thousand-year-old monuments and sites related to its streams, which are recognized by UNESCO as world heritage. Because these places have 1000 years of history. Among these Bukharoyi Sharif, which has the name of blessed Bukhara, Samarkand with its priceless monuments, Shahrissabz, the homeland of our Great Grandfather Amir Temur, Khiva, which is one of the ancient cities of Khorezm, and other ancient cities of ours are considered very sacred in the Islamic world.

The cities of Bukhara and Cairo were declared capitals of "Islamic culture" in 2020. This was announced by Salim bin Muhammad al-Malik, the head of ISESCO, a program for announcing capitals of Islamic culture. The city of Bukhara was included in the UNESCO list as a historical center in 1993. Bukhara region is a major commercial center of the Great Silk Road. There are a lot of architectural monuments, more than 140 of them. In ancient times, the city of Bukhara was called "Museum City". The city of Bukhara is the homeland of seven great Sufis of the Naqshbandi sect. The great representatives of Sufism lived here, engaged in religious and social activities, and contributed to the creation and prosperity of blessed Bukhara, spiritual education and raising the emotional spirit.

There are places of pilgrimage and ancient monuments in the ancient and always popular city of Samarkand. Samarkand city means Registan square, which is considered the heart of the city. It is possible to know that such a definition was given in vain through the following madrasahs. These are: Sherdor, Tillakori and Mirzo Ulugbek madrasahs. The madrasah attracts people with its name and decorative decorations. In addition, the number of foreign tourists and dignitaries is much higher than in other cities. Because the mausoleum of the late First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov is located there. Representatives of the local population often visit here.

In 2000, the city of Shahrisabz, the handicraft center of Kashkadarya region, was included in the UNESCO list. Karshi also has several ancient sites. For example, Oksaroy Kokgumbaz Mosque, Hazrat Imam Mosque and others are famous. Khiva is the greatest wealth of Khorezm, an ancient city. On December 12, 1990, this city was the first in Central Asia to be included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. There are mainly mosques, madrasahs and minarets here: Mausoleum of Pahlavon Mahmud, Ancient Ark, Stone Yard, Olloquli Khan Caravanserai and others. Each decoration of these objects has a long history.

During the last 3-5 years, the number of tourists and pilgrims coming to our country has increased. Therefore, measures are being taken to increase the number of visitors and develop tourism. In particular, on February 9, 2021, a new decree on measures to further develop domestic and pilgrimage tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan was signed.

According to this decree, diversification of tourism products and services aimed at different segments of the tourism market in the Republic, increasing their competitiveness, creating a favorable and favorable domestic and international pilgrimage tourism environment, expanding transport routes, improving the quality of transport services, making travel and recreation safe. A number of works were planned in order to organize the region. Also, starting from March 1, every tourist will be required to pay a tourist fee for using accommodation facilities from local residents.

Apart from them, the two most important religions in the world today are Islam and Christian religions live together peacefully. There are more than 10 sacred and revered Christian and Muslim places and shrines in Uzbekistan.

To this day, there are "additional springs" in the territory of our republic where Christians and Muslims are respected, the most famous of which is located in Bukhara. Along with ancient monuments, sacred shrines, cultural monuments, blessed streets, picturesque places, the above decisions and decrees have been developed in order to attract the attention of tourists and increase their scope. We can clearly see this in the example of the fact that the tourism sector, conducted by the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) on the economic results of the travel and tourism industry, was recorded as one of the five countries with rapid development.

In order to widely promote the potential of pilgrimage tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the world, a group of creative team of "Al-Jazeera" TV channel, which has a high reputation in the Muslim world, will be in the city of Bukhara on February 21-23, 2019. was invited to the First International Pilgrimage Tourism Forum. From April 14, 2021, the show "Uzbekistan" was broadcasted on the Arabic language of this TV channel. From the first issue, which was presented on April 14, it was held at the Hazrat Imam complex and Mushab Usman in Tashkent, the Imam Bukhari complex in Samarkand, the Mir Arab madrasah in Bukhara, and in this city.

There are pictures from the first international pilgrimage tourism forum. One more country, that is, one of the central publications of Turkey, in "Turkiye" newspaper, under the "Gezi" (travel) column, an article entitled "Uzbekistan - our motherland, the cradle of our faith" is brought to the attention of newspaper readers. referred to. In this material, the potential of Uzbekistan in the field of pilgrimage tourism is widely covered, and the available opportunities are discussed.

shrines. Also, the plan of measures for destination promotion of the tourism potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan in foreign countries will be analyzed in a period of no less than 3 days during the holidays of Navroz, Independence Day and New Year, and our religious holidays, Eid al-Fitr. All these opportunities have opened huge opportunities for tourists and vacationers. The conclusion is that it is appropriate to carry out work in such directions as improving the quality of tourism services for the development of tourism by further increasing the number of tourists and pilgrims.

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